

RESOLUTE Binder Characterization Report

SLC12A5 antibody characterization report

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Description:

This report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for Solute Carrier Family 12 Member 5. We used an antibody characterization pipeline based on knockout overexpression (KOOE) and knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of commercial antibodies for *SLC12A5* by immunoblot (Western blot) and immunofluorescence. HuH 7 *SLC12A5* KO and KOOE cell lines are available at RESOLUTE and were used for antibody screening. In order to assess the correct overexpression of *SLC12A5* (coupled to HA-Tag) under doxycycline induction in KOOE cell lines, anti-HA-Tag antibody was utilized.

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Target

Protein name:	SLC12A5, Solute Carrier Family 12 Member 5
Alternative names:	KCC2; K-Cl Cotransporter 2; KIAA1176; HKCC2
Gene name:	SLC12A5
Uniprot ID:	Q9H2X9

Materials

Table 1: Summary of antibodies tested:

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	Clonality	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)
Abcam	ab259969	1014-171-2	monoclonal	Rabbit	0.555

Table 2: Summary of the cell lines used:

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype	Comment
RESOLUTE		-	HuH 7	WT	-
RESOLUTE	CE05P1-S	-	HuH 7	<i>SLC12A5</i> KO ¹	See footnote
RESOLUTE	CE06R6-W	-	HuH 7	<i>SLC12A5</i> KOOE ¹	See footnote

¹ Please contact RESOLUTE (contact@re-solute.eu) to obtain this cell line.

Results

Figure 1: SLC12A5 antibody screening by immunoblot

Figure 1: Analysis of SLC12A5 antibodies by immunoblot.

A) Lysates of HuH 7 (WT, *SLC12A5* KO and *SLC12A5* KOOE) were prepared and 15 μ g of protein were processed for immunoblot with the indicated SLC12A5 antibodies. Antibody dilution used was 1/2000 for the tested antibodies. Expected bandsize: \sim 150 kDa.

B) Lysates of HuH 7 (WT, *SLC12A5* KO and *SLC12A5* KOOE) were prepared and 15 μ g of protein were processed for immunoblot with anti-HA tag antibody. Antibody dilution used was 1/2000. Expected bandsize: \sim 150 kDa. GAPDH was used as housekeeping standard. Expected bandsize: \sim 36 kDa.

Figure 2: SLC12A5 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Figure 2: Analysis of SLC12A5 antibodies by immunofluorescence

HuH 7 WT, *SLC12A5* KO were labelled with a green dye. *SLC12A5* KOOE cells were labelled with a green and a red dye. Parental, KO and KOOE cells were plated on 96 Perkin Elmer PhenoPlates: *SLC12A5* expression was induced with doxycycline in KOOE cells. WT and KO cells were stained with indicated *SLC12A5* antibodies and with Alexa-fluor 594 coupled secondary antibody. KOOE cells were stained with: i) indicated *SLC12A5* antibodies and with Alexa-fluor 594 coupled secondary antibody; ii) anti-HA-Tag antibody and with Alexa-fluor 488 antibody. Acquisition of the green (HA-Tag in KOOE) and red (antibody staining in WT, KO and KOOE) channels was performed. Representative images of the green and red channel are shown. The antibody used and tested dilutions are as follows: ab259969 at 1/100, 1/200 and 1/400.

Methods

Antibodies

All SLC12A5 antibodies are listed in Table 1. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit antibodies are from Cell Signaling (cat. number 7074P2). Alexa-594- conjugated goat anti-rabbit and Alexa-488 conjugated goat anti-rat secondary antibodies are from Invitrogen (cat. number A11012 & A11006)

Cell culture

HuH 7 WT, *SLC12A5* KO, *SLC12A5* KOOE were cultured in Sigma RPMI 1640 medium (cat. number R8758-500) containing 10% Biowest fetal bovine serum (cat. number S1810-500), 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Sigma Aldrich cat. number P-4333-100).

Immunoblot

HuH 7 WT, *SLC12A5* KO and *SLC12A5* KOOE were collected in E1A buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.4, 250mM NaCl, 5.0 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were spun at ~18,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and immunoblot.

Immunoblots were performed with 10% polyacrylamide gels and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes (Amersham cat. number 10600002). Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes are incubated with ECL from Pierce (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with Cytiva Hyperfilm ECL films from Amersham (cat. number 28906837).

Immunofluorescence

HuH 7 WT, *SLC12A5* KO and *SLC12A5* KOOE cells were plated on 96 Perkin Elmer PhenoPlates (cat. number 6005182) and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator. *SLC12A5* expression was induced in KOOE cells under doxycycline (1 µg/ml). Cells were fixed with 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then blocked with 50 µl of PBS with 5% FBS and 0.01% Triton X-100 (IF buffer) for 1 hr at room temperature. Cells were incubated in 30 µl of IF buffer containing the primary SLC12A5 antibodies O/N at 4°C. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 594 (red dye to detect mAB) and Alexa Fluor 488- (green dye to detect HA-Tag only in *SLC12A5* KOOE cells) conjugated secondary antibodies. Cells were washed 3 times in IF buffer once with PBS. Plates were kept at 4°C until imaging.

Imaging was performed using an Opera Phenix Plus High-Content Screening System equipped with a 40x objective. All cell images represent a single focal plane. Figures were prepared using CellProfiler to merge the pictures taken with different channels.

Data availability

Report available at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/resolute/>

<http://re-solute.eu>

References